

Hepatitis B and C Virus Coinfection and Screening Participation in Nasarawa State, Nigeria: A Facility- and Community-Based Study

Awayimbo Ruth Jaggu

Department of Public Health, Global Health and Infectious Diseases Institute (GHIDI), Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

David Ishaleku

Department of Public Health, Global Health and Infectious Diseases Institute (GHIDI), Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria; Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Natural and Applied Sciences, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

Akolo Yohanna Jaggu

Department of Community Medicine, University of Abuja Teaching Hospital, Gwagwalada, Abuja, Nigeria

Olubunmi Iyabode Ojji

Department of Guidance and Counselling, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria

Oluwatosin Adeoye Adefila

Department of Public Health, Global Health and Infectious Diseases Institute (GHIDI), Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria; Department of Community Medicine, University of Abuja Teaching Hospital, Gwagwalada, Abuja, Nigeria

Samuel Chukwuemeka Obasi

Department of Health Policy and Management, Global Health and Infectious Diseases Institute (GHIDI), Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria; National Primary Health Care Development Agency, FCT, Abuja, Nigeria

Anthonia Chiwendu Chukwuemeka

Department of Public Health, Global Health and Infectious Diseases Institute (GHIDI), Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria; Department of Public Health, Federal Ministry of Health and Social Welfare, Abuja, Nigeria

Aishat Temitope Kasali

Department of Public Health, Global Health and Infectious Diseases Institute (GHIDI), Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

Joyce Samuel Zalanga

Department of Public Health, Global Health and Infectious Diseases Institute (GHIDI), Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

Akyala Ishaku Akyala

Department of Public Health, Global Health and Infectious Diseases Institute (GHIDI), Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria; Department of Health Policy and Management, Global Health and Infectious Diseases Institute (GHIDI), Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

Abstract

Background: Hepatitis B virus (HBV) and hepatitis C virus (HCV) coinfection accelerates liver disease progression and increases the risk of adverse clinical outcomes, complicating clinical management. Globally, HBV–HCV coinfection is relatively uncommon but clinically significant. In Africa, reported prevalence varies across settings. In Nigeria, hepatitis screening is largely indication-based—typically occurring during antenatal care, blood

More Information

How to cite this article: Jaggu AR, Ishaleku D, Jaggu AY, Ojji OI, Adefila OA, Obasi SC, Chukwuemeka AC, Kasali AT, Zalanga JS, Akyala AI. Hepatitis B and C Virus Coinfection and Screening Participation in Nasarawa State, Nigeria: A Facility- and Community-Based Study. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2026;4(2):138-47.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2026.4(2).22

Keywords:

Hepatitis B virus (HBV),
Hepatitis C virus (HCV),
Coinfection,
Screening uptake,
Nigeria.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

donation, or in response to clinical suspicion—which may contribute to delayed diagnosis and linkage to care. However, Data on HBV–HCV coinfection and screening participation in Nigeria remain limited.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 852 adults in Nasarawa State, Nigeria, recruited from facility- and community-based settings in Keffi, Lafia, and Akwanga Local Government Areas between May and November, 2025 using multistage sampling. Structured questionnaires collected sociodemographic information and prior hepatitis screening history. Blood samples were tested for hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) and anti-HCV antibodies using rapid diagnostic tests and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, with polymerase chain reaction confirming coinfection. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and Chi-square tests, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The overall prevalence of HBV–HCV coinfection was 1.6%, highest in Keffi (2.5%), with no significant geographic variation. Screening uptake was 42% for HBV and 40% for HCV. Willingness to participate in free screening programs was high (92.4%) across locations.

Conclusion: Although HBV–HCV coinfection prevalence was low, screening coverage remains suboptimal, potentially contributing to delayed diagnosis and linkage to care. Strengthening routine hepatitis testing and implementing targeted community-based strategies are essential to improve early detection and support hepatitis elimination efforts in endemic settings.

Introduction

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) and Hepatitis C virus (HCV) infections continue to represent a substantial yet often overlooked public health burden Globally, contributing substantially to chronic liver disease, cirrhosis, hepatic decompensation, and hepatocellular carcinoma [1,2]. Although effective preventive and therapeutic interventions are available, many infections remain undiagnosed because they are frequently asymptomatic for prolonged periods [3,4]. Delayed diagnosis permits progressive hepatic injury, resulting in preventable morbidity, premature mortality, and escalating healthcare costs [5].

Despite Global prioritization of diseases like HIV, tuberculosis, and malaria, viral hepatitis has received comparatively limited attention in National and International health agendas. Sub-Saharan Africa bears a disproportionate burden of chronic viral hepatitis, with considerable heterogeneity across countries and regions [6]. In Nigeria, this has translated into inadequate screening coverage, low public awareness, and limited integration of hepatitis services into routine healthcare. Individuals with HBV–HCV coinfection are particularly vulnerable, as coinfection accelerates liver disease progression, increases the risk of adverse clinical outcomes, and complicates clinical management, compared to mono-infected patients [7,8].

Screening is central to hepatitis prevention and control strategies; however, access to and participation in testing services varies substantially across populations [9]. Facility-based screening programs may not adequately capture individuals outside formal healthcare settings, particularly in rural and semi-urban communities. Socioeconomic constraints, low health literacy, and structural health system barriers further restrict screening uptake, leaving a substantial pool of undiagnosed infections. Consequently, reliance on facility-based data alone may underestimate the true

burden of HBV–HCV coinfection and obscure important epidemiological patterns [10].

Understanding the distribution of HBV–HCV coinfection and patterns of screening participation across both healthcare facilities and community setting is essential for informing targeted interventions [11]. This study examines these dynamics in Nasarawa State, Nigeria, generating context-specific evidence to identify gaps in screening coverage and support strategies aimed at improving early detection and strengthening hepatitis control efforts in endemic settings.

Methodology

Study Design and Setting

This cross-sectional study was conducted between May and November 2025 in Nasarawa State, North-Central Nigeria. Participants were recruited from both healthcare facility-based and community-based settings, including the Federal Medical Centre (FMC), Keffi, and selected communities within Lafia and Akwanga Local Government Areas.

FMC, Keffi, is a major tertiary healthcare facility serving Nasarawa State and neighbouring parts of the Federal Capital Territory. It provides comprehensive clinical and preventive services, including outpatient care, diagnostic laboratory services, and infectious disease screening, and receives patients from urban and peri-urban areas. Participants in Keffi were enrolled during routine healthcare visits. Community recruitment in Lafia and Akwanga targeted urban, semi-urban, and rural populations to capture hepatitis B and C epidemiology and screening participation beyond healthcare-seeking individuals.

Study Area

The study was conducted in Nasarawa State, located in North-Central Nigeria, which shares boundaries with the Federal Capital Territory, Kaduna, Plateau, Taraba, Benue, and Kogi States [12]. The population comprises urban and rural communities, with livelihoods largely based on civil service, agriculture, trading, and small-

scale enterprises. Three Local Government Areas (LGAs) — Lafia, Keffi, and Akwanga — were purposively selected to capture varying levels of urbanization, healthcare access, and sociodemographic characteristics. Lafia, the state capital, is predominantly urban with tertiary and secondary healthcare facilities. Keffi is semi-urban, hosting academic institutions and commercial centres, while Akwanga is largely semi-urban to rural, with primary and secondary health facilities.

Nasarawa State has a mixed healthcare delivery system, including primary, secondary, tertiary, and community-based providers. Viral hepatitis screening and treatment services are available but unevenly distributed, predominantly in urban centres. Inclusion of both urban and semi-urban/rural LGAs allowed comparative assessment of HBV–HCV coinfection prevalence, screening awareness, and participation across different geographic and health system contexts.

Figure 1: Map of Nasarawa State, Showing Study Location on Colour Yellow
 Source: [13]

Study Population

The study included adults aged ≥18 years who resided in selected communities (Akwanga and Shabu in Lafia LGA; Andaha and Akwanga Central in Akwanga LGA) or attended the Federal Medical Centre, Keffi, during the study period. Participants were recruited irrespective of sex, occupation, education, or socioeconomic status. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants, with confidentiality and voluntary participation assured. Inclusion of both community- and facility-based populations enabled a comprehensive assessment of HBV and HCV prevalence, coinfection patterns, and screening behaviours across diverse segments of Nasarawa State.

Sample Size

The minimum sample size was calculated using Cochran’s formula [14], assuming a 95% confidence

level, 5% margin of error, and an estimated HBV prevalence of 12.8% [15]. To account for the multistage sampling design, the calculated sample size was multiplied by 1.5, and a 10% non-response rate was added. The final target was 284 participants per location, ensuring adequate representation across facility- and community-based settings in Keffi, Lafia, and Akwanga.

Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique was employed to recruit participants from both community and facility settings. In the first stage, study locations were selected using simple random sampling by balloting, whereby eligible facilities and Local Government Areas (LGAs) were listed and randomly selected through a ballot method. One tertiary healthcare facility (Federal Medical Centre, Keffi) was selected from the available facilities, and two LGAs were similarly selected using the same balloting procedure.

In the second stage, participant selection was conducted using systematic random sampling. Within the selected healthcare facility, participants were recruited proportionate to the clinic patient load. In the selected LGAs, wards were randomly chosen, followed by systematic household sampling using a calculated sampling interval [27]. Eligible adults in selected households were consecutively enrolled until the required sample size was achieved. This design ensured randomness at each stage and proportional representation across locations, capturing both facility- and community-based populations. Detailed procedures, including ward and household selection, are provided in Supplementary Material.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Adults aged ≥18 years who resided in the selected communities or attended the study health facility and provided informed consent were eligible. Individuals aged <18 years, those who were critically ill, mentally incapacitated, non-residents, or who declined consent were excluded.

Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured, interviewer-administered questionnaire that captured sociodemographic characteristics (age, sex, educational attainment, occupation), health-seeking behaviours and prior participation in screening programs. The adopted questionnaire was pretested in a population with similar characteristics, and feedback from the pilot informed refinements in wording, sequencing, and clarity to enhance reliability and validity. Data collection was conducted by trained research assistants who underwent standardized training covering ethical considerations, informed consent procedures, questionnaire administration, and accurate documentation of responses. Data quality was ensured through daily supervision, on-site review of

completed questionnaires, and prompt resolution of inconsistencies. Participant confidentiality was ensured through the use of unique identification codes, and all completed questionnaires were securely stored to maintain data completeness, consistency, and integrity.

Sample Collection and Laboratory Testing:

Using standard aseptic techniques, 5 mL of venous blood was collected from each consenting participant by trained phlebotomists into properly labelled, sterile, single-use vacutainer tubes (plain and K₂EDTA) [27]. Blood samples collected in plain tubes were allowed to clot at room temperature and subsequently centrifuged to obtain serum. Serum samples were promptly separated and maintained under cold-chain conditions at 2–8 °C prior to laboratory analysis.

Samples collected in EDTA tubes were processed to obtain plasma for molecular testing, including hepatitis B virus (HBV) DNA and hepatitis C virus (HCV) RNA assays, and were stored at –80 °C until analysis. All specimens were transported in accordance with standard biosafety, cold-chain, and specimen integrity protocols to prevent haemolysis and nucleic acid degradation.

Laboratory Analysis

Rapid Diagnostic Testing (RDT)

Rapid diagnostic tests were used for the initial screening of hepatitis B and C infections. Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) was detected using the One-Step Cassette Style HBsAg Rapid Test (ACON Laboratories Inc., USA), while anti-hepatitis C virus (anti-HCV) antibodies were screened using the Wondfo One-Step Anti-HCV Rapid Test (Wondfo Biotech Co., Ltd., China). According to manufacturer documentation, both assays demonstrate high diagnostic performance, with reported sensitivity and specificity exceeding 99%. All tests were performed in accordance with the manufacturers' instructions. Results were interpreted visually within the recommended time frame. The presence of a control band validated each test, while the presence or absence of a test band indicated reactive or non-reactive results.

Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) Testing

Using standardized commercial kits based on the Abbott Microparticle Enzyme Immunoassay platform (Abbott Laboratories, USA), all serum samples were tested for HBsAg and anti-HCV antibodies irrespective of RDT results. ELISA is a solid-phase immunoassay that detects viral antigens or antibodies through specific antigen–antibody binding and enzyme-mediated colorimetric detection. Serum samples were added to antigen- or antibody-coated microtiter plates and incubated to allow immune complex formation. Following incubation, unbound components were removed through automated washing, and enzyme-

labelled conjugates were added to bind to target complexes. A chromogenic substrate was then introduced, producing a colorimetric reaction proportional to the analyte concentration. Optical density values were measured using a microplate reader, and results were interpreted according to manufacturer-defined cut-off values. Positive and negative controls were included in every run to ensure analytical validity and assay integrity. ELISA served as the confirmatory serological method, providing high-sensitivity detection of HBsAg and anti-HCV antibodies in both clinical and community-based populations.

Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) Testing

Plasma samples were analyzed for the presence of HBV DNA and HCV RNA using real-time polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR) in designated molecular laboratories under strict contamination control procedures to confirm ELISA-reactive samples and establish HBV–HCV coinfection status. HBV DNA was extracted using the QIAamp DNA Mini Kit (Qiagen, Germany) and amplified using the HBV Real-TM Qual Kit. HCV RNA was extracted using the QIAamp Viral RNA Mini Kit and detected using one-step RT-qPCR targeting the highly conserved 5' untranslated region (5' UTR) of the HCV genome [27]. To ensure assay reliability, positive, negative, and no-template controls, as well as internal amplification controls, were included in each run. Results were interpreted based on exponential amplification curves within validated cycle threshold (Ct) ranges. All procedures were performed in accordance with MIQE (Minimum Information for Publication of Quantitative Real-Time PCR Experiments) and WHO guidelines, with adherence to established biosafety and quality control standards. This approach enabled accurate molecular detection of HBV and HCV and confirmation of coinfection status in the study population.

Quality Control

Quality control measures were applied throughout the study to ensure data accuracy and reliability. All laboratory assays (RDT, ELISA, and PCR) followed standardized protocols with appropriate controls included in each run. Procedures were conducted in designated laboratories under strict biosafety and contamination-prevention measures, in line with manufacturer instructions, MIQE standards, and WHO recommendations. Data collection and entry were performed by trained personnel and routinely cross-checked for completeness and consistency. These measures ensured the integrity and reproducibility of laboratory and epidemiological findings.

Ethical Consideration

The study was conducted in accordance with established ethical standards for research involving human participants. Ethical approval was obtained from the Nasarawa State Ministry of Health Ethics

Committee (NHREC Protocol No: 18/06/2017. Approval date: 20/12/24 to 31/12/25). The approved protocol detailed the study objectives, methodology, eligibility criteria, and anticipated risks and benefits. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants following clear explanation of the study purpose and procedures, with assurance of voluntary participation and the right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Participant confidentiality was maintained through anonymization of data and secure storage, with access restricted to authorized research personnel. The study adhered to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the Nigerian National Code of Health Research Ethics. To ensure inclusivity, study information was communicated in simple language and, where necessary, in local dialects for participants with limited literacy.

Data Analysis

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel 2019 for cleaning, coding, and validation and subsequently exported to IBM SPSS Statistics version 26 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA) for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize participants' sociodemographic characteristics and laboratory findings. Continuous variables were presented as mean ± standard deviation, while categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages.

The primary outcome was PCR-confirmed HBV–HCV coinfection, defined as the concurrent detection of hepatitis B virus DNA and hepatitis C virus RNA using real-time polymerase chain reaction. Coinfection prevalence was calculated as the proportion of participants meeting this criterion.

The secondary outcome was participation in hepatitis B and C screening. Screening participation was classified as “good” or “poor” based on predefined criteria

derived from participants’ self-reported prior screening history.

Associations between categorical variables were assessed using the Chi-square (χ^2) test to examine relationships between study location and HBV–HCV coinfection prevalence, as well as between study location and screening participation. All statistical tests were two-tailed, and statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Data integrity was ensured through cross-verification of totals and proportions across rapid diagnostic tests, enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, and polymerase chain reaction results prior to final analysis.

Results of the Study

A total of 852 participants were enrolled across Lafia, Akwanga, and Keffi LGAs. The mean age was 37.4 ± 12.9 years, with 57.7% aged 20–39 years; 51.8% were female. Most were married (54.8%) and had tertiary education (56.3%). Major occupations included civil service (26.2%), students (21.4%), and farming (16.9%), with a heterogeneous income distribution (Table 1).

PCR-confirmed HBV–HCV coinfection prevalence was 1.6% (14/852), highest in Keffi (2.5%) and lowest in Lafia (0.7%), with no significant differences across locations ($\chi^2 = 2.760$; $p = 0.252$) (Table 2). RDT and ELISA results were largely concordant.

Screening uptake was modest (HBV 42.1%; HCV 40.5%), and awareness of available programs was low overall (25.7%), varying by location. Participation among aware individuals was highest in Keffi (73.3%). Routine healthcare visits were infrequent, yet willingness to engage in free screening was high (92.4%), and 94.5% supported integration of hepatitis testing into routine care (Table 3). Overall, 53.1% demonstrated good participation, with significant geographic variation ($\chi^2 = 54.749$, $p < 0.001$), highest in Lafia (68.7%) and lowest in Keffi (37.7%) (Table 4).

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants (n = 852) across Lafia, Akwanga, and Keffi LGAs, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Variables	Local government area of resident			Total N=852
	Lafia n=284	Akwanga n=284	Keffi n=284	
Age group (Years)				
18-19	15(5.3%)	10(3.5%)	7(2.5%)	32(3.8%)
20-29	100(35.2%)	83(29.2%)	76(26.8%)	259(30.4%)
30-39	80(28.2%)	94(33.1%)	59(20.8%)	233(27.3%)
40-49	43(15.1%)	52(18.3%)	63(22.2%)	158(18.5%)
50-59	30(10.6%)	29(10.2%)	57(20.1%)	116(13.6%)
≥60	16(5.6%)	16(5.6%)	22(7.7%)	54(6.3%)
Mean±SD	35.6±12.7	36.3±11.9	40.4±13.5	37.4±12.9
Sex				
Male	149(52.5%)	142(50.0%)	120(42.3%)	411(48.2%)
Female	135(47.5%)	142(50.0%)	164(57.7%)	441(51.8%)
Marital status				
Single	151(53.1%)	96(33.8%)	56(19.7%)	303(35.6%)

Married	122(43.0%)	150(52.8%)	195(68.7%)	467(54.8%)
Separated	0(0.0%)	11(3.9%)	15(5.3%)	26(3.1%)
Divorced	0(0.0%)	8(2.8%)	0(0.0%)	8(0.9%)
Widowed/Widower	11(3.9%)	19(6.7%)	18(6.3%)	48(5.6%)
Level of education				
No Formal Education	8(2.8%)	45(15.8%)	8(2.8%)	61(7.2%)
Primary	29(10.2%)	18(6.3%)	31(10.9%)	78(9.2%)
Secondary	109(38.4%)	77(27.1%)	47(16.5%)	233(27.3%)
Tertiary	138(48.6%)	144(50.7%)	198(69.7%)	480(56.3%)
Occupation				
Student	91(32.0%)	58(20.4%)	33(11.6%)	182(21.4%)
Unemployed	51(18.0%)	33(11.6%)	37(13.0%)	121(14.2%)
Artisan	0(0.0%)	33(11.6%)	40(14.1%)	73(8.6%)
Farmer	48(16.9%)	52(18.3%)	44(15.5%)	144(16.9%)
Private sector employee	26(9.2%)	30(10.6%)	53(18.7%)	109(12.8%)
Civil Servant	68(23.9%)	78(27.5%)	77(27.1%)	223(26.2%)
Monthly income range				
< ₦20,000	128(45.0%)	68(23.9%)	49(17.3%)	245(28.8%)
₦20,000–₦50,000	84(29.6%)	62(21.8%)	50(17.6%)	196(23.0%)
₦50,000–₦100,000	48(16.9%)	117(41.2%)	90(31.6%)	255(29.9%)
> ₦100,000	24(8.5%)	37(13.1%)	95(33.5%)	156(18.3%)

Note: Values are presented as n (%) for categorical variables and mean ± SD for continuous variables. SD = Standard Deviation; LGA = Local Government Area. Percentages may not total 100 due to rounding.

Table 2: Prevalence of HBV–HCV Coinfection Across Lafia, Akwanga, and Keffi LGAs, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Variables	Local government area of resident			Total N=852	χ^2	P-value
	Lafia n=284	Akwanga n=284	Keffi n=284			
HBV-HCVRDT					5.374	0.068
Positive	1(0.4%)	5(1.8%)	8(2.8%)	14(1.6%)		
Negative	283(99.6%)	279(98.2%)	276(97.2%)	838(98.4%)		
HBV-HCV ELISA					2.760	
Positive	2(0.7%)	5(1.8%)	7(2.5%)	14(1.6%)		
Negative	282(99.3%)	279(98.2%)	277(97.5%)	838(98.4%)		
HBV-HCV PCR					2.760	0.252
Positive	2(0.7%)	5(1.8%)	7(2.5%)	14(1.6%)		
Negative	282(99.3%)	279(98.2%)	277(97.5%)	838(98.4%)		

Note: Values are n (%) for categorical variables. RDT = Rapid Diagnostic Test; ELISA = Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay; PCR = Polymerase Chain Reaction. χ^2 = Chi-square test statistic. $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Table 3: Participation in Hepatitis B and C Screening Across Lafia, Akwanga, and Keffi LGAs, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Variables	Local government area of resident			Total N=852
	Lafia n=284	Akwanga n=284	Keffi n=284	
Ever undergone hepatitis B screening				
Yes	113(39.8%)	122(43.0%)	124(43.7%)	359(42.1%)
No	171(60.2%)	162(57.0%)	160(56.3%)	493(57.9%)
Ever undergone hepatitis C screening				
Yes	113(39.8%)	124(43.7%)	108(38.0%)	345(40.5%)
No	171(60.2%)	160(56.3%)	176(62.0%)	507(59.5%)
Aware of any hepatitis B and C screening programs available in your community or hospital				
Yes	23(8.1%)	106(37.3%)	90(31.7%)	219(25.7%)
No	261(91.9%)	178(62.7%)	194(68.3%)	633(74.3%)
If yes, participated in any screening program	n=23	n=106	n=90	n=219

Yes	12(52.2%)	55(51.9%)	66(73.3%)	133(60.7%)
No	11(47.8%)	51(48.1%)	24(26.7%)	86(39.3%)
the main reason for not participating in any screening program	n=261	n=178	n=194	n=633
Cost	26(10.0%)	15(8.4%)	40(20.6%)	81(12.8%)
Fear of diagnosis	2(0.8%)	12(6.7%)	5(2.6%)	19(3.0%)
Lack of awareness	214(82.0%)	133(74.7%)	101(52.1%)	448(70.8%)
No reason	1(0.4%)	5(2.8%)	24(12.4%)	30(4.7%)
No symptoms	12(4.6%)	9(5.1%)	13(6.7%)	34(5.4%)
Time	6(2.3%)	4(2.2%)	11(5.7%)	21(3.3%)
Visit to the healthcare facility for medical check-ups				
Regularly	24(8.5%)	64(22.5%)	64(22.5%)	152(17.8%)
Annually	6(2.1%)	18(6.4%)	102(35.9%)	126(14.8%)
Occasionally	152(53.5%)	156(54.9%)	100(35.2%)	408(47.9%)
Never	102(35.9%)	46(16.2%)	18(6.4%)	166(19.5%)
Participate in a free hepatitis B and C screening program if offered				
Yes	273(96.1%)	264(93.0%)	250(88.0%)	787(92.4%)
No	11(3.9%)	20(7.0%)	34(12.0%)	65(7.6%)
Hepatitis B and wvC screening should be part of routine health check-ups				
Strongly agree	281(98.9%)	274(96.5%)	250(88.0%)	805(94.5%)
Agree	3(1.1%)	10(3.5%)	34(12.0%)	47(5.5%)
Regular screening for hepatitis B and C				
Very important	263(92.6%)	196(69.0%)	137(48.2%)	596(70.0%)
Important	18(6.3%)	69(24.3%)	115(40.5%)	202(23.7%)
Neutral	1(0.4%)	17(6.0%)	23(8.1%)	41(4.8%)
Unimportant	1(0.4%)	0(0.0%)	6(2.1%)	7(0.8%)
Very unimportant	1(0.4%)	2(0.7%)	3(1.1%)	6(0.7%)
Motivation to participate in a screening program for hepatitis B and C				
Free service	127(44.7%)	156(54.9%)	149(52.5%)	432(50.7%)
Awareness campaign	99(34.9%)	70(24.6%)	107(37.7%)	276(32.4%)
Doctor's recommendation	50(17.6%)	41(14.4%)	24(8.4%)	115(13.5%)
Family or community involvement	8(2.8%)	17(6.1%)	4(1.4%)	29(3.4%)

Note: χ^2 -Chisquare test statistic, n (%) for categorical variables

Table 4: Level of Participation in Hepatitis B and C Screening Across Lafia, Akwanga, and Keffi LGAs, Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Variable	Local government area of resident			Total N=852	χ^2	P-value
	Lafia n=284	Akwanga n=284	Keffi n=284			
Level of participation					54.749	<0.001*
Good	195(68.7%)	150(52.8%)	107(37.7%)	452(53.1%)		
Poor	89(31.3%)	134(47.2%)	177(62.3%)	400(46.9%)		

Note: * Test significant at 95% χ^2 -Chisquare test statistic p < 0.05 is statistically significant.

Discussion

Our study shows that HBV–HCV coinfection remains low among adults in Nasarawa State, with an overall prevalence of 1.6%. Despite this, coinfection has significant clinical implications, as it increases the risk of compounded liver injury and complicates management compared to mono-infections. The observed prevalence is lower than reported in high-risk populations locally and internationally—for instance, studies in Turkey and Nigeria found rates of 4.5% and

5.1% among HIV-infected individuals [15,16]. Similarly, hospital-based and community surveys in India, Southeast Nigeria, and Ethiopia reported coinfection rates of 0.2%, 0.58%, and 1.2%, respectively, reflecting that dual infection is uncommon in general populations despite shared transmission routes [17-19]. In Ghana, seroprevalence was <1 per 1000 participants [20]. These findings indicate that while coinfection is rare in general adult populations, targeted surveillance and

prompt treatment remain critical due to rapid progression to liver complications.

Our study also highlights disparities in screening participation across locations. Only just over half of participants demonstrated good engagement, with the highest participation in Lafia and lowest in Keffi. These geographic differences align with evidence from Nigeria and sub-Saharan Africa showing that communities with integrated health services, routine outreach, and sustained health education exhibit higher screening uptake [21]. In contrast, Lagos State reported only 3.5% of adults ever tested despite high prevalence, emphasizing gaps between awareness and action [22].

Awareness of screening programs in our study was low (25.7%), particularly in Lafia, with lack of awareness (70.8%) and cost (12.8%) being the main barriers. High willingness to participate in free screening (92.4%) suggests that socioeconomic factors rather than lack of interest are primary constraints. Evidence from broader African studies demonstrates that integrated outreach, free or subsidized testing, and community engagement significantly improve uptake [21,23,24].

Although coinfection prevalence is low, missed diagnoses carry substantial consequences, including liver fibrosis, hepatocellular carcinoma, and preventable mortality. Strengthening routine and targeted screening is essential. Our findings support WHO recommendations to integrate hepatitis testing into primary care, maternal and child health services, and HIV programs [25]. The perceived importance of regular screening among participants (70% rated it “very important”) indicates strong community readiness that can be leveraged through tailored awareness campaigns, outreach programs, and free or low-cost testing [26].

Conclusion

HBV–HCV coinfection in Nasarawa State is relatively low (1.6%), yet gaps in awareness, screening participation, and equitable access pose significant public health challenges. Geographic disparities and low routine testing create a reservoir of undiagnosed infections that risk progression to chronic liver disease. Encouragingly, high willingness to engage in free screening indicates strong community readiness. Strengthened, community-centered interventions—including routine integration of viral hepatitis testing, targeted awareness campaigns, and removal of financial and structural barriers—are critical. These measures will facilitate early detection, improve linkage to care, and advance Nigeria’s viral hepatitis elimination goals while reducing long-term morbidity and mortality

Strengths and Limitations of the Study

The study’s use of PCR confirmation and combined facility- and community-based sampling enhances the

reliability and generalizability of the findings within Nasarawa State. Limitations include its cross-sectional design which prevents assessment of temporal or causal relationships. Additionally, while PCR testing confirmed infection status, some behavioural or screening history data were self-reported, which may introduce recall bias.

Authors Contribution

A.R.J and A.Y.J, Conceptualized and Designed the study. A.R.J, A.Y.J, O.I.O, O.A.A, A.T.K, S.C.O, A.C.C, and J.S.Z. Data Collection. A.R. J, O.I. O, A.Y. J, and O.A.A. data curation, A.I.A., D.I., A.R.J., and A.Y.J data analysis. A.R.J. and A.Y.J. Original Manuscript Drafting. A.R.J, A.Y.J, O.I.O, O.A.A, A.T.K, S.C.O., A.C.C, and J.S.Z. Revised the Manuscript for Intellectual and Scientific content and developed the Results and Discussion sections. A.I.A., D.I, Supervision. All authors critically reviewed, edited, and approved the final version of the manuscript for publication.

Conflict of Interest

None.

Funding

This research received no external funding.

Data Availability

The datasets generated and analyzed during this study are not publicly available due to ethical and confidentiality considerations but are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declarations

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Conflict of Interests

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Clinical trial number

Not applicable.

Reference

- [1] Os A, Cc E bakpa, Fc O, Ci A, Oa A, Pi M, et al. Prevalence and risk implications of Hepatitis B and C Viruses in a University community in. 2024;7(2):155–63.
- [2] Victor AO, Akyala AI, Godwin AA, Saidat BF, Ismaila I, Awayimbo JR, et al. Prevalence and Risk Factors of Hepatitis B Virus Infection among Patients in Tertiary Healthcare Facilities in Nasarawa State, Nigeria: A Cross-Sectional Study. International Research Journal of Gastroenterology and Hepatology. 2025;8(1):66–78.
- [3] Patil CA, Potnuri L, Siddharaju P, Maheshwari PK, Manu OP, Mamatkulovna MN. The Systemic Burden of Chronic Hepatitis C: A Comprehensive Review of Hepatic and Extrahepatic Complications in the Era of Direct-Acting Antivirals. Scholars International Journal of Traditional and Complementary Medicine. 2025;8(09):216–23.
- [4] Jaggu AR, Akyala AI, Jaggu AY, Obasi SC, Aboh VO, Olatinwo IA. Evolutionary insights of hepatitis B

virus genotypes among seropositive-drug- experienced HIV patients in Nigerian tertiary health Centre. 2025;

[5] Abdelhamed W, El-Kassas M. Hepatitis B virus as a risk factor for hepatocellular carcinoma: There is still much work to do. *Liver Res* [Internet]. 2024;8(2):83–90. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livres.2024.05.004>

[6] Holt B, Fernandez M, Nguyen D, Delima D, Duy LD, Gaspar M, et al. Embedding viral hepatitis into primary healthcare: results of a strategic landscape analysis in Vietnam and the Philippines. *Lancet Reg Health West Pac* [Internet]. 2024;44:100990. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanwpc.2023.100990>

[7] Adepoju VA, Udah DC, Ezenwa CA, Ganiyu J, Lawal SM, Haruna JA, et al. Toward Universal Health Coverage: What Socioeconomic and Clinical Factors Influence Health Insurance Coverage and Restrictions in Access to Viral Hepatitis Services in Nasarawa State, Nigeria? *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2024;21(10).

[8] Kim HN, David H. Spach. Hepatitis B Coinfection. 2021;(Figure 4):1–46.

[9] World Health Organization. Information sheet (Viral hepatitis B and C burden of disease, WHO policy adoption status in countries, 2025). 2025;2024(July).

[10] Javaid A, Riyaz A, Masood B, Hamayun Khan MT, Lakho M, Shaikh Z. Assessing the Role of Community-Based Screening in Early Detection of Hepatocellular Carcinoma in Hepatitis B and C at a Tertiary Care Hospital. *Pakistan Journal of Medical & Health Sciences*. 2023;17(11):311–4.

[11] Faniyi AA, Okesanya OJ, Manirambona E, Oso TA, Olaleke NO, Nukpezah RN, et al. Advancing public health policies to combat Hepatitis B in Africa: Challenges, advances, and recommendations for meeting 2030 targets. *Journal of Medicine, Surgery, and Public Health* [Internet]. 2024;2(January):100058. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.glmedi.2024.100058>

[12] About Nasarawa State – Official Website of Nasarawa State [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jun 17]. Available from: <https://nasarawastate.gov.ng/about-nasarawa-state/>

[13] Chunwate BT, Marchant RA, Jew EKK, Stringer LC. Understanding Local Perspectives on the Trajectory and Drivers of Gazetted Forest Reserve Change in Nasarawa State, North Central Nigeria. *Land (Basel)*. 2025;14(7):1–29.

[14] Ahmed SK. How to choose a sampling technique and determine sample size for research: A simplified guide for researchers. *Oral Oncology Reports* [Internet]. 2024;12(September):100662. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oor.2024.100662>

[15] Awayimbo Jaggu R, Belinda Eseohé M, Clementina Ogu A, Yohanna Jaggu A, Ishaleku D, Ishaku Akyala A. Viral Hepatitis Co-infection Impact on Response to Antiretroviral Therapy and HIV Disease

Progression: Virologic and Immunological Indices Outlook. *Biomedical Sciences*. 2021;7(4):124.

[16] Senoglu S, Yesilbag Z, Karaosmanoglu HK, Aydin OA. Prevalence of HBV/HCV co-infection and associated risk factors in people living with HIV. *Hepat Mon*. 2020;20(4):0–5.

[17] Chaudhary R, Fatima S, Sharma P, Singh DP, Verma RK. Burden of hepatitis B , C , and coinfection from a tertiary care hospital in Western Uttar Pradesh : A cross-sectional study. 2025;15(3):581–5.

[18] Nnakenyi ID, Uchekukwu C, Nto-Ezimah U. RPrevalence of hepatitis B and C virus co-infection in HIV positive patients attending a health institution in southeast Nigeria. *Afr Health Sci*. 2020;20(2):579–86.

[19] Mohammed N, Kassim J, Aliyi AA, Abdurebi MJ. Prevalence of viral hepatitis B and C infection and associated factors among pregnant women in southeast Ethiopia: community-based cross-sectional study. *Front Glob Womens Health* [Internet]. 2025;6(February):1–10. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fgwh.2025.1508788>

[20] Adanusa M, Adjei G, Eliason S, Amoah S, Benson C, Sirikiyi I, et al. Sero-prevalence of Hepatitis B and C at a Primary Healthcare centre in Ghana. *AfricArXiv*. 2023;24(4):29–37.

[21] Akabuiké OMA, Aworh MK, Uzoebo NL, Erwat J, Agukwe O, Ngong K, et al. Evaluating hepatitis B screening, prevalence, vaccination coverage, and linkage to care in Abuja, Nigeria: insights from a cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health* [Internet]. 2024 Dec 1 [cited 2025 Jan 10];24(1):1–11. Available from: <https://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-024-21017-3>

[22] Odukoya OO, Odeyemi KA, Odubanjo OM, Isikekpei BC, Igwilo UU, Disu YM, et al. Hepatitis B and C seroprevalence among residents in Lagos State, Nigeria: A population-based survey. *Niger Postgrad Med J*. 2022;29(2):75–81.

[23] KOMI LS, CHIANUMBA EC, YEBOAH A, FORKUO DO, MUSTAPHA AY. Advances in public health outreach through mobile clinics and faith-based community engagement in Africa. *Iconic Res Eng J*. 2021;4(8):159–78.

[24] Spearman CW, Andersson MI, Bright B, Davwar PM, Desalegn H, Guingane AN, et al. A new approach to prevent, diagnose, and treat hepatitis B in Africa. *BMC Global and Public Health* [Internet]. 2023;1(1):1–11. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s44263-023-00026-1>

[25] World Health Organization. Full-Final-Who-Ghss-Hiv-Vh-Sti_1-June2022 (3). 2022;(June):1–110. Available from: https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/hq-hiv-hepatitis-and-stis-library/full-final-who-ghss-hiv-vh-sti_1-june2022.pdf?sfvrsn=7c074b36_9

[26] Akabuike OM. Addressing the Silent Epidemic of Hepatitis B Virus: Awareness , Screening and Vaccination Efforts in Abuja , Nigeria. :1–20.

[27] Elwany S, Medanni A, Eid M, Aly A, El-Daly A. Sphenoid sinus pneumatization patterns and their

clinical significance: a CT-based study. Research Square. Preprint. 2024. Available from: <https://assets-eu.researchsquare.com/files/rs-8490509/v1/d851cba6-1540-41f5-a3e6-71e6a994806e.pdf>

